

On the Persson-Strang's Identity for the Legendre Polynomials

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Abstract:

We show an alternative proof of an identity given by Persson-Strang for the well known Legendre polynomials.

Keywords: Zudilin's identity, Legendre polynomials, Persson-Strang's identity.

Introduction

The Legendre's polynomials (Legendre, 1785) $P_n(x)$, $-1 \leq x \leq 1$, can be defined via the following recurrence relation (Lanczos, 1972; Chihara, 1978; Oldham, & Spanier, 1987):

$$(n + 1) P_{n+1} = (2n + 1)x P_n - n P_{n-1}, P_0 = 1, P_1 = x, n = 1, 2, \dots, \quad (1)$$

hence:

$$P_2 = \frac{1}{2}(3x^2 - 1), P_3 = \frac{1}{2}(5x^3 - 3x), P_4 = \frac{1}{8}(35x^4 - 30x^2 + 3), \dots \quad (2)$$

These polynomials also are determined univocally through the conditions (Sommerfeld, 1964; Broman, 1989):

$$\int_{-1}^1 P_m(x) P_n(x) dx = 0, m \neq n, P_n(1) = 1, \forall n, \quad (3)$$

therefore:

$$\int_{-1}^1 x^m P_n(x) dx = 0, m < n, \quad (4)$$

and the Laplace's integral formula (Chihara, 1978; Oldham, & Spanier, 1987; Sommerfeld, 1964; López-Bonilla, López-Vázquez, & Torres-Silva, 2015; Doman, 2016; Foupouagnigni, & Koepf, 2020) gives an alternative way to generate the expressions (2):

$$P_n(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} (x + \sqrt{x^2 - 1} \cos \beta)^n d\beta, n = 0, 1, 2 \dots \quad (5)$$

or equivalently:

$$P_n(x) = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor} (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \binom{2n-2k}{n} x^{n-2k}. \quad (6)$$

Persson-Strang (2003), Amdeberhan et al. (2021), Bulnes, López-Bonilla, & Prajapati (2023) obtained the interesting identity:

$$\int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{P_{2n+1}(x)}{x} \right]^2 dx = 2, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (7)$$

then in Sec. 2 we use an identity of Zudilin (2014) to generate an alternative proof of (7).

Persson-Strang's identity

Zudilin (2014) and López-Bonilla, & Prajapati (2023) deduced the following property:

$$[P_m(x)]^2 = \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} \binom{m+k}{m} \binom{2k}{k} \left(-\frac{1-x^2}{4}\right)^k, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (8)$$

therefore:

$$Q(m) \equiv \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{P_m(x)}{x} \right]^2 dx = \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} \binom{m+k}{m} \binom{2k}{k} \frac{(-1)^k}{4^k} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{(1-x^2)^k}{x^2} dx, \quad (9)$$

however, it easy to obtain the expression:

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{(1-x^2)^k}{x^2} dx = -\frac{2(4^k)}{\binom{2k}{k}}, \quad (10)$$

then from (9) and (10):

$$Q(m) = -2 \sum_{k=0}^m (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \binom{m+k}{m} = -2 {}_2F_1(-m, m+1; 1; 1). \quad (11)$$

On the other hand, we know the relation (Quaintance & Gould, 2016):

$$\sum_{k=0}^m (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \binom{z+ky}{m} = (-y)^m, \quad y \neq 0, \quad (12)$$

which for $z = m$ and $y = 1$ implies the result:

$$\sum_{k=0}^m (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \binom{m+k}{m} = (-1)^m = P_m(-1) = {}_2F_1(-m, m+1; 1; 1), \quad (13)$$

hence from (9), (11) and (13):

$$\int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{P_m(x)}{x} \right]^2 dx = 2(-1)^{m-1}, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (14)$$

which reproduces the Persson-Strang's identity (7) when m is odd.

Remark.-In Bulnes, López-Bonilla, & Prajapati (2023) it was proved the property:

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{1}{x} P_{2n+1}(x) dx = \frac{2(-4)^n (n!)^2}{(2n+1)!}. \quad (15)$$

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